

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

It gives me great pleasure to announce the third regular issue of 2022. I would like to thank all the authors for their sound research and the editorial board for the extremely valuable reviews and suggestions for improvement. These contributions, together with the generous support of the consortium members, enable us to run our journal and maintain its quality.

Still, I would like to expand our editorial board: If you are a tenured associate professor or above with a good publication record, please apply to join our editorial board. We are also interested in receiving high-quality proposals for special issues on new topics and emerging trends.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce four accepted papers involving nine authors from four different countries.

Sedef Demirci and Seref Sagiroglu from Turkey introduce TwitterBulletin which is a real-time automated news categorization tool for Twitter based on a novel machine learning approach built on a public dataset with a large number of real-world Turkish news tweets. Also in the social media domain, Vitor Garcia dos Santos and Ivandré Paraboni from Brazil apply pre-trained language models to the classification of personalities from texts, focusing specifically on the Myers-Briggs personality model. Mohd Khaled Y. Shambour and Esam A. Khan from the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia discuss in their paper a hyper-heuristic approach to optimize the distribution process of pilgrims over Mina tent camps by selecting one among four predefined low-level heuristics to generate a new one, and discuss solution quality and convergence rate. Nahia Ugarte, Mikel Larrañaga and Ana Arruarte from Spain conduct a systematic mapping review that explores the use of recommender systems in formal learning stages.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

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